

A new species of the genus *Muangnua* (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora: Helicarionidae: Durgellinae) from North Vietnam

Ivaylo K. Dedov

Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 2 Gagarin Street, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria,
idedov@gmail.com

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Abstract: Based on its anatomy, a new species of the genus *Muangnua* is described from Northern Vietnam. This is the third species in this genus, which is endemic to Southeast Asia, and the first one described from Vietnam. The newly found species expands the geographical range of the genus with more than 650 kilometres to the northeast.

Keywords: distribution, Tam Dao National Park, taxonomy, tropical semi-slugs, Vinh Phuc Province

Introduction

The type species of the genus *Muangnua* Solem, 1966 – *M. limax* Solem, 1966, was described from Doi Suthep in Chiang Mai Province, Northern Thailand, at 1100 m above sea level (Solem, 1966). Another species of the same genus, *Muangnua arborea* Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan, 2019, was added, based on specimens from Phu Suan Sai, Na Haeo District, Loei Province, in the Northeast of Thailand (Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan, 2019). According to Schileyko (2002), the genus *Muangnua* is characterised by a shell reduced to partially calcified cap having only single remains of coiling and completely covered by fused shell laps. Other diagnostic characters include: tail long, very slender, with hooked caudal horn; reproductive apparatus simple, without appendages; spermatheca long, reaching 2/3 of way to albumen gland. Based on the external morphology, *Muangnua* is similar to the genus *Parmarion* Fischer, 1856 (Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan, 2019). According Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan (2019), the genus evolved at high altitudes and might be distributed over a wide area.

They expected further species in this genus to be discovered in other areas with high altitude.

In this study, the third species of the genus *Muangnua* is described based on a specimen from the vicinity of Tam Dao Town, Vietnam, at altitude of 1000 m.

Materials and methods

In the course of a survey on the invertebrate fauna of Tam Dao National Park, Vinh Phuc Province, Vietnam, a living mature specimen of unknown semi-slug was collected in a tropical forest near the town of Tam Dao (Fig. 1). The specimen was found inside of a decaying trunk on 16 October 2023.

After photographical documentation in situ, the specimen was processed following the methods in Nitz et al. (2009). It was relaxed in a jar with water and some drops of the surfactant SUPRALAN-UF until fully stretched and dead. The dead semi-slug was cleaned of mucus in a sieve under cold running water. For preservation, 96% ethanol was injected with a syringe into the body cavity through the

terminal tip of the sole. The specimen was then placed in ethanol (96%) and left for some hours. It was stored in 70% ethanol.

The reproductive system and the shell of the semi-slug were examined and photographed under a stereomicroscope Zeiss Discovery V12 and digital camera Panasonic, Lumix DMC-TZ31.

All measurements are in millimetres and have been taken from the preserved specimen. The general methods of dissecting follow Wiktor (2000).

Used abbreviation: IBER-BAS – Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.

Results

Order Stylommatophora A. Schmidt, 1855
Superfamily Helicarionoidea Bourguignat, 1877
Family Helicarionidae Bourguignat, 1877
Subfamily Durgellinae Godwin-Austen, 1888
Tribe Durgellini Godwin-Austen, 1888
Genus *Muangnua* Solem, 1966
Type species: *Muangnua limax* Solem, 1966, OD.

Muangnua vumanhi sp. nov.

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Holotype: Vietnam, Northern, Vinh Phuc Province, Tam Dao Town, tropical forest up to the town, on and under tree bark overgrown with tree-dwelling fungi, and in decaying trunks; N21.46067° E105.64878°, 1055 m, 16.10.2023, leg. I. Dedov, N. Simov, R. Bekchiev, M. Langourov. The holotype is deposited in the collection of the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Coll. IBER-BAS 40601/1).

Differential diagnosis

Muangnua vumanhi sp. nov. differs from *Muangnua limax* Solem, 1966 by its larger size (39 mm instead of 21.6 mm), more intense light-ochre-brown body colouration and its bi-colour (whitish/dark and grey-blackish) upper tentacles. Caudal horn is less

Fig. 1. *Muangnua vumanhi* sp. nov. – the type-locality in the Tam Dao National Park, North Vietnam.

prominent in the new species. Anatomically, it differs by its: larger bulbous atrium, presence of long and well-defined epiphallus, relatively shorter bursa copulatrix, reaching about of half way to albumen gland (instead 2/3 in *M. limax*).

Muangnua vumanhi sp. nov. differs from *Muangnua arborea* Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan, 2019 in its more yellowish body colouration, smaller-sized groups of pigment spots, the absence of the white “Y” stripe on dorsal side of the body and the presence of darker stripes on the middle of the dorsal shallow groove. The caudal horn not so prominent. Anatomically, it differs in its larger bulbous atrium, thicker vagina, and longer epiphallus.

Description

Colouration: Primary colour of anterior body is light-ochre-brownish. At the posterior part of the body, numerous yellowish-ochre pigment spots, grouped in various sized patches. Dorsally, brown-blackish line

Fig. 2. *Muangnua vumanhi* sp. nov. (holotype) in a natural environment. A – active crawling animal; B – colouration of the foot in a live animal; C – tubercles in non-active position; D – close-up view of the unusual coloration of the head, neck and tentacles.

extending from the visceral hump to 2/3 of the posterior part of the body. This colouration laying in shallow groove (not a keel as usual) (Fig. 2A). Mantle and visceral hump very intensively coloured, both with yellowish-ochre and brown-blackish pigmentation. Brown-blackish pigments form two lateral stripes but not as intensely-dark as the dorsal brown-blackish line (Fig. 2A). Head and neck whitish, with two dark-greyish lateral zones (Fig. 2D).

Lower tentacles purely whitish, while the upper tentacles unusually coloured: lower parts whitish; upper parts, including eyes, dark-grey-blackish (Fig. 2D). Slime is transparent and colourless.

Body (Fig. 2A): Slender, elongated. Total length of the preserved adult specimen 39 mm, body width 8 mm, mantle length 17 mm. The bubble-shaped visceral hump lies in the body cavity. The mantle fully covers the shell. Dorsum with a little horn-like

Fig. 3. *Muangnua vumanhi* sp. nov. (holotype) – fixed body. A – top view; B – lateral view; C – close-up view of the genital pore, the contrast around the genital pore is enhanced; D – close-up view of the brown-blackish coloured dorsal shallow groove; E – structure of the caudal horn, the contrast around the caudal horn is enhanced.

prolongation at its posterior end. Caudal horn structurally well-formed, distinct, weakly projecting beyond body outline (Fig. 3E).

Visceral hump lying in “V” shaped body groove on top of foot. Mantle fully covering the shell (Figs 2A-D; 3A, B, D).

Body cavity not enlarged into posterior part of foot, which is fully muscular. Sole narrow, subdivided in 3 zones; central zone lighter than lateral zones in the live animal (Fig. 2B). In mature animal, genital pore clearly visible (Fig. 3C). In resting position (when the animal is contracted), the skin-wrinkles form pointed tubercles, in which yellowish-orange pigment is concentrated (Fig. 2C).

Fig. 4. *Muangnua vumanhi* sp. nov. (holotype) – vestigial shell. A – dorsal view of the shell; B – lateral view of the shell; C – ventral view of the shell.

Shell (Fig. 4): Reduced to partially calcified plate, no whorls; shell length 6.3 mm, shell width 3.8 mm. Apex not prominent. Shell completely covered.

Anatomy (Fig. 5)

Maturity was determined prior to dissection by examining the genital pore under a binocular microscope (Fig. 3C).

Atrium (AT) is relatively large and bulbous.

Penis (P) relatively large, wider in its portion close to the atrium. Musculus retractor penis (MRP) thin and short, attaches to the penis at proximal end,

the atrium and reaching about halfway to albumen gland. Albumen gland (AG) small, pale-yellowish.

Etymology

The species is named after the great friend of Bulgaria and famous Vietnamese biologist professor Vu Quang Manh, in recognition of his contribution to the knowledge of the invertebrate fauna of Vietnam and acknowledgement of the perfect organisation of the field studies that made possible collecting the present specimen.

Discussion

The newly described species has all the characteristics allowing to classify it into the genus *Muangnua*: reduced shell, simple reproductive apparatus without appendages and long spermatheca. Presently, the species is known from its type locality only: relatively high tropical forests in Northern Vietnam. The species was found during the day, deep in a decaying trunk, which was rich in mycelium and fruiting bodies of tree-dwelling fungi.

The genus evolved at high altitudes and might be distributed over a wide area (Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan, 2019). The discovery of a new semi-slug species in a relatively poorly explored mountainous region of Northern Vietnam is very likely (Páll-Gergely et al., 2015; Dedov et al., 2019). It is possible that the species has a mostly-hidden lifestyle and uses fungi as food. The protective behaviour with quickly flipping and twisting their foot when touched, registered in *Muangnua arborea* (see Tumpeesuwan & Tumpeesuwan, 2019) was not observed in *Muangnua vumanhi* sp. nov. In the resting stage, the animal looks “bristled”, which probably is a passive protective camouflage that helps it blend in with the grain structure of the substrate (Fig. 2C).

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Fig. 5. Reproductive system of *Muangnua vumanhi* sp. nov. (holotype) Abbreviations: AT – atrium; P – penis, MRP – musculus retractor penis, EP – epiphallus, VD – vas deferens; V – vagina, BC – bursa copulatrix, SO – spermoviduct, AG – albumen gland.

near to the epiphallus. Epiphallus length almost equal to penis, curved and pinched near the middle. Vas deferens (VD) relatively long and thick, inserting into epiphallus apically.

Vagina (V) long, relatively thick and tubular. Bursa copulatrix (BC) long, finger-like, starts close to

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References

- Dedov I., Schneppat U., Vu M.Q., Huy N.Q. 2019 A new semislug of the genus *Laocaia* (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Helicarionidae) from Vietnam. *ZooKeys* 846: 19–30.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.846.34372>
- Nitz B., Heim R., Schneppat U.E., Hyman I., Haszprunar G. 2009 Towards a new standard in slug species descriptions: the case of *Limax sarnensis* Heim & Nitz n. sp. (Pulmonata: Limacidae) from the Western Central Alps. *Journal of Molluscan Studies* 75: 279–294.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/mollus/eyp030>
- Páll-Gergely B., Hunyadi A., Ablett J., Luong H.V., Naggs F., Asami T. 2015 Systematics of the family Plectopylidae in Vietnam with additional information on Chinese taxa (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Stylommatophora). *ZooKeys* 473: 1–118.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.473.8659>
- Schileyko A.A. 2002 Treatise on recent terrestrial pulmonate molluscs. 9. Helicarionidae, Gymnarionidae, Rhysotiniidae, Ariophantidae. *Ruthenica Supplement* 2 (10): 1167–1307.
- Solem A. 1966 Some non-marine mollusks from Thailand, with notes on the classification of the Helicarionidae. *Spolia Zoologica Musei Hauniensis* 24: 7–110.
- Tumpeesuwan C., Tumpeesuwan S. 2019 *Muangnua arborea*, a new semislug (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora, Helicarionidae, Durgellinae) from Loei Province, northeastern Thailand. *ZooKeys* 894: 19–32.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.894.38327>
- Wiktor A. 2000 Agriolimacidae (Gastropoda: Pulmonata) – a systematic monograph. *Annales Zoologici* 49: 347–590.